

Burning Both Ends: A Conceptual Model for International Student Employee Burnout Prevention and Supervisory Practice in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

As growing numbers of international students engage in on-campus student employment, the burnout they experience remains underexamined. This conceptual article introduces a practitioner-informed, theory-driven Burnout-Responsive Supervision Model to explore how International Student Employees (ISEs) in global higher education navigate the dual identity of student and employee. The model identifies five core stressor domains—conflicting cultural norms, labor expectations, limited supervision, marginalization, and compliance pressures—that can lead to imposter syndrome, emotional exhaustion, and disengagement. It positions supervision as a pivotal factor in either exacerbating or relieving these challenges. Drawing on peer leadership, trauma-informed care, and Restorative Practices, this article urges institutions to adopt inclusive, culturally responsive supervisory strategies. By addressing both structural and cultural drivers of burnout, the model offers a holistic framework to enhance student staff development and support ISEs more effectively within global campus communities.

Introduction

International students play a vital role in global higher education, not only as degree-seeking scholars but as contributors to campus operations and culture through meaningful on-campus employment (Glass & Gesing, 2018). These roles offer income, work exposure, and a pathway to connection, belonging, and professional growth. However, international student employees (ISEs) must navigate dual identities as students and workers, balancing academic responsibilities with workplace obligations. This is compounded by microaggressions, tokenization, and inadequate culturally responsive support (Elliot & Smith, 2022). Burnout among ISEs often emerges as a trauma-informed response to sustained cultural dissonance and inadequate supervisory support,

leading to disengagement and diminished career confidence (Mori et al., 2009). Reframing burnout as a systemic issue calls for responsive supervision that affirms identity and builds capacity (Su, 2018). This article introduces a burnout-responsive supervision model that examines how identity conflict, cultural mismatch, and inconsistent support contribute to burnout, and how intentional, equity-centered supervision can promote inclusive and affirming work environments for ISEs.

Problem and Significance

On-campus employment is widely recognized as a high-impact practice that supports international students' integration, purpose, and professional

development (Taylor & Sandoval, 2024). However, once hired, ISEs often face challenges shaped by language barriers, cultural adjustment, visa restrictions, and sociopolitical stress (Mori et al., 2009), factors rarely acknowledged by supervisors or shared by domestic peers. While existing

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research independently addresses international student engagement, burnout, and supervision (Lee, 2017; Glass & Gesing, 2018; Yin et al., 2024), the intersection of these domains, particularly through the lens of ISEs, remains underexamined. On-campus employment is often undertheorized as a mechanism for engagement and inclusion among international students, and supervisory practices tend to follow one-size-fits-all models that overlook identity-informed needs (Elliot & Smith, 2022). Subsequently, ISEs receive limited guidance and instead rely on peer support networks when navigating workplace challenges (Lee, 2017).

Leask (2009) argues that Internationalization at Home must extend beyond the formal curriculum to include the hidden curriculum, where student affairs and services (SAS) and the supervision of student employees play a pivotal role. This article addresses a persistent gap by framing supervision as a site for cultural affirmation and relational care. It proposes a burnout-responsive model as a practice-based approach to internationalization.

Theoretical Frameworks

This article introduces a practitioner-informed, exploratory conceptual model grounded in four intersecting theoretical frameworks. Kim's International Student Identity Model (2012) highlights how international students navigate bicultural identity and power asymmetries, which shape their workplace experiences. The Job Demands–Resources Model (Demerouti et al., 2001) explains burnout as arising when job demands outpace available resources, a dynamic applicable to student workers managing academic, cultural, and emotional stressors. Restorative Practices emphasize relational trust, empathy, and accountability in supervision, particularly across cultural lines. Trauma-Informed Supervision (Creamer, 2023) emphasizes the importance of safety, identity-based stress, and emotional proximity. These frameworks' relevance to intercultural supervision and identity development was applied iteratively to organize emergent stressor domains and guided the development of a model outlining supervisory strategies to enhance the inclusion of ISEs within global campus communities.

The Conceptual Model

This model frames burnout among ISEs due to overlapping stressors often ignored in campus employment. **Figure 1** offers four interconnected supervisory practices that address identity, culture, and systemic support to create more affirming and sustainable work environments.

Stressors Leading to Burnout

First, Cultural Dissonance and Role Conflict. ISEs often come from hierarchical cultures with different norms around authority and boundaries, making it challenging to balance academic and work responsibilities while adapting to unfamiliar supervision and peer dynamics, intensifying their stress. Second, Internalized Expectations. Many ISEs internalize expectations of perfection and gratitude, leading them to avoid seeking help or disclosing challenges for fear of appearing weak. This perfectionism often masks deeper stress and feelings of isolation. Third, Supervision

Figure 1. Burnout-Responsive Supervision Model for ISE

Inconsistency. Supervisory structures in SAS are usually transactional, leaving ISEs with minimal guidance and assumed self-reliance.

Furthermore, ISEs often undertake additional labor that is rarely acknowledged, rendering their contributions to campus life essential yet invisible (Lee, 2017). Fourth, Marginalization and Underrepresentation. ISEs are often the only non-domestic staff members, leading to feelings of tokenization and doubts about being hired for merit. Microaggressions, such as assumptions about their competence or language skills, intensify anxiety and drive overperformance, further isolating them from team culture. Finally, Structural and Political Pressures. ISEs face restricted work hours and limited job access due to visa, citizenship, and work-study constraints. Those who secure roles often feel underpaid, replaceable, and fearful that mistakes could threaten their status; these are structural, not personal, stressors. These stressors contribute to ISE burnout, appearing as emotional exhaustion, impostor syndrome, withdrawal, and disengagement (Parkman, 2016).

Supervisory Practices

First, Relational Supervision. Proactive and consistent engagement fosters trust, helping supervisors identify concerns early. Normalizing challenges and encouraging open dialogue allows ISEs to feel supported, viewing supervision as guidance rather than management. Second, Feedback and Role Clarity. Clear expectations and timely, strengths-based feedback reduce ambiguity and stress. Responsibilities should align with each student's capacity and background to support growth within U.S. workplace norms. Third, Accountability and Peer Support. ISEs benefit from peer mentorship and co-leadership (Mitchel & Kay, 2013). This supports intercultural learning and promotes equitable labor. Inclusive, team-based practices elevate ISE voices and contributions, reducing isolation. Finally, Culturally Responsive and Affirming Practice. Supervisors

should tailor support to address identity-based stressors, affirm ISE experiences, and guide career development concerning visa, language, and cultural realities.

Future Directions

ISEs contribute more than labor; they enrich campus culture, foster intercultural learning, and model global citizenship. Supporting them is not just operational, but a matter of equity and inclusion. Supervisors must be trained in restorative practices, cultural fluency, and compliance-informed approaches to provide affirming, responsive support. Institutions should invest in onboarding, evaluation, and leadership development tailored to ISEs. Supervision must be recognized as a high-impact practice that promotes student retention, well-being, and a positive campus climate. Supporting international students already contributing to our campuses is critical to building truly global institutions and advancing Internationalization at Home (Leask, 2009). Burnout-responsive supervision is not an add-on but foundational to fostering equity, belonging, and sustainability.

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